

Competitive Strategy of Tie-Dyed Cloth Smes in Facing the Existence of Batik Cloth in Yogyakarta City

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ABSTRACT

The aims of this study were to determine the factors that are considered a buyer in the purchase of tie-dyed cloth in the Yogyakarta City and want to know the tie-dyed cloth competitive strategy faces batik cloth in the domestic and international markets. This research was conducted in tie-dyed cloth industry centers of the city of Yogyakarta. Type of this research is a descriptive study. The data used in this study are primary data and secondary data. Comparative analysis of the attributes of tie-dyed cloth and batik cloth were analyzed by competitive profile matrix. The results recommend that the tie-dyed cloth competitive strategy faces batik cloth in the domestic and international markets is a tie-dyed cloth should be positioned as a product that is unique than batik cloth.

Keywords: Tie-Dyed; Batik; CPM; Competitive Strategy.

INTRODUCTION

By the enactment of batik cloth as an Indonesian cultural heritage by UNESCO (Lusiani and Rani, 2012) is the pride and challenge for Indonesia to keep the preservation of the national culture of batik cloth amid the onslaught of foreign culture as a result of globalization. Result of batik cloth status as a world heritage by UNESCO, the batik cloth significantly had high competitiveness (Novandari, 2013; Setyanto, et al, 2015). In the past, batik cloth only worn by Indonesia in Java and it confined to the class of patrician palaces with very strict rules. In the process, batik has become the national dress of Indonesia that wear by Indonesian people across the country on various occasions, even batik has become the hallmark of Indonesia.

Amid the competition of batik cloth that is so tight has pushed the batik makers created a variety of innovations, including the inheritance fabric. Indonesian ancestor has developed a counteraction colors technique with a more simple way which is called tie-dyed cloth. Tie-dyed cloth is a fabric that has a way of giving color similar to batik by dyeing hurdles way. The difference, in batik wear "*malam*" as the color barrier material, while in tie-dyed cloth which is used is a variety of others types of materials as the color barrier (Zulaikhah, 2010). These fabrics play an important role in various ceremonies or religious through message from the delivered motive (Geertz, 1992; Solomon and Ezra, 2015). Characteristic of the tie-dyed fabric is the boundary between the two colors are not sharp, even the colors overlapping each other. Perhaps because of this reason, which gives uniqueness and artistic attractiveness. Especially in Yogyakarta City, the types of fabric often used for scarves, kemben, headbands, belts, sinjang and others. Besides its usefulness, the colors of tie-dyed cloth have a spiritual meaning and indicate the social status position (Djumena, 1990).

The amount of small industrial business unit tie-dyed cloth has prompted the government to pay more attention to its development. Development mission of small and medium industries are expanding job creation through the creation and development of the job vacancy, increase the income of the public society is more evenly (Singla and Goyal, 2015), spread the development activities to optimally utilize domestic resources (indigenous resources) efficiently within the framework of deepening the industrial structure of the sustainable development principle and environmental insight

(Kachba, et al, 2012), increase exports and make small and medium industries as a place for the preservation and development of cultural arts (Disperindagkop, 2002; Atmojo, 2015).

Design and model on tie-dyed cloth has its characteristics and own unique. In addition, it has an attractive selling point. Efficiency in all aspects (Singla and Goyal, 2015) as well as the right competitive strategy needed to face the competition with batik cloth that existed earlier. Batik cloth as a cultural heritage better known is a major competitor in the segment of buyers tie-dyed cloth. To that end, tie-dyed cloth artisans in Yogyakarta and Solo need to prepare appropriate strategies for the successful of tie-dyed cloth in the domestic and international market. Based on the description above, this study aims to (1) Understand the factors that considered by the buyer in the purchase of tie-dyed cloth in Yogyakarta and Solo city, (2) Understand the competitive strategy of tie-dyed cloth in the face of big names batik cloth in the domestic and international markets.

LITERATURE REVIEWS

Tie-Dyed Cloth

Tie-dyed cloth is the dyeing / coloring way of textile materials by binding the material according to the pattern so that there is counteraction to produce a pattern on the cloth. Cloths are dyed with tie-dyed technical called with *jumputan* cloth, *tritik*, rainbow and *sasirangan*. Tie-dyed cloth has a high artistic value because its manufacture requires persistence and thoroughness, so many women are making it (Yusuff and Andrew, 2012). To create a tie-dyed cloth needed a binder from a rope and mastery of the bonding techniques. There are several bonding techniques are often used include: 1) Tie Techniques, (2) Stich Techniques, (3) Fold Techniques, (4) Marbling, (5) Knotting, (6) Press, (7) Kruching (8) Pleat Techniques.

Tie-dyed cloth is counteraction staining techniques because in certain places are not penetrated by the dye solution caused the bond and pull the stitches (Solomon and Ezra, 2015). According to Susanto (1995), tie-dyed also commonly known as "*jumputan*" because the coloring is done through the pinch (drawn or pulled) and then tied with a rope yang tidak menyerap zat warna (Zulaikhah, 2010). Tie-dyed cloth is conceptually very easy and simple manufacturing techniques, this also that characterize and uniqueness of tie-dyed cloth. The uniqueness of the lines contained in the motive formed from the color difference between the bound and unbound section. So with only one dyeing step will be obtained color combinations that produce a motive. Binder used varies, such as cotton yarn, polyester, rope, rubber or elastic. In addition to using a binder, to obtain varying patterns and motifs often accompanied by a bond in the filler material in the form of nuts, seeds, stones and beads or using coins. Tie technique is made by taking a piece of cloth to be made into the circle shape or the location of the center of the circle by pinching the middle, then the bottom of the area taken tied with string or binders other.

After the bonding is complete, the material is ready to be dipped into a solution of color. Larsen (1976) stated there are three basic bonding techniques are known, namely:

- a) A single bond: a single bond technique is done by giving a bond on the cloth with one bond alone, in order to get a binding motif.

Figure 1. Technique and Single Bond Motif

- b) A double bond: In a double bonding technique, the cloth was given a bond of more than one bond in order to get more than one motive bond or a double

Figure 2. Double Bind Technique and Motif

- c) A cross bond: In the crosslinking technique, bonding are done crosswise so obtained binding motifs in the form of crossed each other.

Figure 3. Cross Bond Technique and Motif

Product Attributes

Analysis of consumer satisfaction of the attributes of tie-dyed cloth supplied by the seller or by the craftsmen influencing the purchasing decision in the tie-dyed cloth consumers themselves. Product attributes can provide a clear picture and that is important considered by consumers (Suharyati, 2013). Most consumers will consider some of the attributes that are provided as services provided by the sellers then the price and quality of products obtained can already be considered to meet the level of consumer satisfaction or buyers. Then a strategic location and reached easily also are an important factor because of the ease of access would facilitate consumers in making transactions. Based on the description, it can be said that the product attributes affect consumer buying behavior (Kartika, et al, 2010).

Product attributes as well as the development of products or services that involves the determination of the benefits to be provided in terms of quality and features of sold products. Functional satisfaction gained from consumers based on product attributes has a percentage of 80% compared to other factors (Cahyo, 2013).

Assessment of consumers of a product can be seen from the indicators the attributes of the product, such as product pricing, quality of raw materials, availability of raw materials, labor absorption, environmental impact, creativity motif, the speed of production, distribution, sales, and technology mastery. It is not obtainable in the market. All the attributes that must be considered. Other attributes that are considered as *ceteris paribus* is the quality of service to consumers.

Services aimed at facilitating the buyers when they shop at the store. Things that can facilitate buyers consist of customer service, the ability to sell, service transactions in the form of an easy payment method. Thus, the service is not included in attributes assessed if the products are compared assessed with other products.

Competitive Advantage

In a further development it was realized that the competition does not always require every product should have an absolute advantage over competitors. This is the thrust behind the theory of comparative advantage. David Ricardo in Ismawanto (2009) states that a country that suffered a loss or disadvantage in obtaining second absolute commodity when compared with other countries still can have a profitable trade. Less efficient countries will specialize in the production and export of commodities that have a smaller absolute losses. The state of this commodity has a comparative advantage and reverse the country also imported commodities that have a comparative disadvantage. This is known as the Law of Competitive Advantage (Salvatore, 2002).

A product that already has a comparative advantage will give a positive benefit if it can be pushed into a competitive advantage in front of consumers. Competitive advantage can be sustained through the implementation prioritize value creation strategy (Barney, 1991), which supported the power of capital and institutional capital (Oliver, 1997). According to Porter (1980), there are four components of a product can be classified as highly competitive products, namely:

- i) Factorial condition, namely the position of a country in the factors of production needed to compete in a particular industry.
- ii) Demand conditions, the nature of the domestic demand for the products or services of a particular industry
- iii) The existence of related industries and supporting industries internationally competitive
- iv) Strategy, structure, and competitive company that domestic conditions which determine how companies are formed, organized and managed as well as the nature of domestic competition.

Competitive Strategy

Strategy can be defined as a means to reach the purposes, because a strategy is basically a scheme to reach the intended target (Umar, 2003). According to Jauch and Glueck (1988), the purpose of the strategy (united plan) is binding on all companies into one.

Competitive strategy is "how companies can compete in a certain market share" (Johnson and Scholes, 1993). Competitive strategy made at the level of the business unit with the aim to anticipate the competition in an industry that is strictly for certain products. Innovation cannot be released with the terminology of the company's strategy, because innovation is a key factor of growth and increased competitiveness of companies (Vega-Jurado, et al, 2015).

Developing a competitive strategy is the development of a general formula how the business will compete, what should be the goal and what policies are needed to achieve these goals. According to Porter (1980), the purpose of competitive strategy for a business unit in an industry is to find a position in the industry in which the company can respond to competitive pressures or may affect the competitor pressure positively. Effective competitive strategy covering for offensive or defensive action in order to create a safe position against the five forces of competition.

Appropriate strategy needs to be formulated through the stages of strategic management. The management strategy is the art and science of formulating, implementing, and evaluating cross-functional decisions that enable the organization to achieve its goal (David, 2013). As implied in the definition, management strategy focuses on integrating management, marketing, finance / accounting, product/operations, research and development, and computer information systems to achieve organizational goals. Strategy Management as a set of decisions and actions that resulted in the formulation and implementation of a plan designed to achieve the goals of a company/organization. Strategic formulation is the initial action in each organization's strategic management activities. The formulation of the strategy is an instrument of leadership and is a process. As a process, it determines the desired of organization in the future and how the effort to achieve it. Strategic formulation as a component of the strategic management served to clarify the goals and objectives, selecting various policies, notably in obtaining and allocating resources, and create a guideline in translating organization policy (Afrilita, 2013)

RESEARCH METHODS

Basic Methods and Research Location Determination

Competitive strategy research tie-dyed cloth in Yogyakarta City uses descriptive analytical method, the research focused on the actual problems during this time. Data collected initially conceived, described and analyzed (Surakhmad, 1994). The research location is determined with purposive method. It is the choice of group subject was based on the characteristics or specific traits that are considered to have a close relation with the characteristics or properties of the

previously known populations. Yogyakarta and Solo is the center tie-dyed fabric industry in Indonesia. This city has two central areas of tie-dyed fabric development.

Sources and Types of Data

Data used in this study are primary data and secondary data. Primary data, that is data obtained directly from the object, which is the center of tie-dyed in Yogyakarta and Solo, and employees of government / institution directly related to the tie-dyed cloth. Key-informant or informants in this study include the employees of the trades SMEs and Industrial and Trade Department in Yogyakarta and Solo, Textile Association Management of Indonesia, Board of the National Crafts Council of Yogyakarta and Solo, and the tie-dyed cloth craftment. Determination of key-informant determined by purposive. Secondary data used in this study include the overall secondary data obtained from the Central Statistics Agency.

Data Analysis Methods

To determine the competitive position of tie-dyed cloth and their competitors in the batik cloth used CPM (Competitive Profile Matrix) analysis. CPM assessment is measured by the critical success factors / attributes (Arijanto 2010) and rating variations (Danang, 2010 and Capps and Glissmeyer, 2012). Identification of critical success factors aims to analyze the determinants of the success of the strengths and weaknesses in a tie-dyed cloth products. Identification of success factors and weighting is done with key informants businessman tie-dyed cloth. According Harisudin (2011), especially for companies that are still small and medium enterprises that still have limited access and information delivery system, the CPM is an alternative of competitive strategy analysis tool that effectively and efficiently (Fleisher and Bensoussan (2003), Harisudin (2011), David (2013), Capps and Glissmeyer (2012) and Sohel, et al, (2014).

Effectiveness and efficiency can be seen from the known of value ratio of each critical success factors were assessed (head to head). After knowing the competitive position of the product with a competitor's product, then the next step is to formulate an alternative strategy of competing products/services. Alternative strategies can be developed through a mechanism to encourage critical success factors that have a high weighted values serve as the brand image of the product through an intensive strategy while reducing the weaknesses of critical success factors that have the lowest weighted value.

Aggregation of replies from all key informants conducted by sources of triangulation techniques. Triangulation is a technique that checking the data validity which is utilizing something else outside of that data for the purpose of checking or as a comparison of the data and increase the validity (Moleong, (2007) and Meijer, et al., (2002) and Ziyani, et al., (2004). In this research, triangulation technique used is the technique of triangulation sources. The goal for researchers to obtain authentic information from sources that can be compared between one and other sources through different perspective, then the reality would be founded (Sutopo, 2002; Yeasmin and Rahman, 2012).

Figure 4. Schematic of Source Triangulation

After the identification of critical success factors, continued with weighting determination of each of the key success factors, where each factor is measured on the scale (weights) are the same for each product, but with varying ratings making it easier to do a comparative analysis. Weight of the CPM shows the relative importance of the factors to be decisive in the company's success in industry. The rank is an assessment based on the success factors that assessed over a competitor's product. The rating is then multiplied by the weighting of each of the critical success factors for each product being compared. The weighted value (scores) is the results achieved after each weight multiplied by each value ranking. The highest weighted value shows the superiority of the product over a competitor's product.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In developing the industrial centers of cloth dye, there are things that need to be considered by the Government. Things to consider by the Government could be a boost or obstacle. The definition of a boost is everything for these activities will be acquired for the benefit of regional development and welfare, while the meaning of an obstacle is anything that causes the development industrial centers. In the efforts to develop an industrial center cloth dye which inevitably results in waste, then to establish a policy should be compared with approaches alternative products. The important critical success factors were considered in developing the central government tie-dyed cloth are:

1. Product Pricing

The price of the products is the important success factors that will directly determine the consumer will decide purchase a product or not. Results of this purchase to blood/energy for companies to be able to continue the product process. Product pricing of tie-dyed cloth generally are more expensive than batik cloth produced by printing techniques or combinations, but when compared with the results of batik cloth, the tie-dyed cloth more competitive according to the consumer. With this advantage, tie-dyed cloth has the potential to take a market of batik cloth. Alternatively, work on the market segments that the purchasing power of people under batik cloth.

2. Quality of products

The quality of a product generally reflects the price of its products (Zeithaml, 1988). Tie-dyed cloth quality in general is not as fancy as batik cloth. This is not out of the manufacturing process is "a little trial and error". Sharpness and detail execution results can not be observed as well as the process of making batik cloth. Thus, it is not surprising that the price of tie-dyed cloth under batik cloth. Efforts to improve the quality through scrutiny in the manufacturing process (Zeithaml, 1988 and Valipour, et al, 2012) has been carried out by the craftsmen, but the end result of the resulting color is still can not expect in the process of making batik cloth.

3. Absorption of Labor

Tie-dyed cloth production requires energy character has special skills with a high level of patience. Labor requirements like this are usually owned by women. So it is not surprising that almost all the workers involved are women. No labor from men, but only found on the stage of the design (the earliest stage of the production process of tie-dyed fabric).

Workers absorbed in tie-dyed cloth industry mostly consist of women with the status of housewives and older women who have been in this industry many years ago. An irony if want to develop creative industries, but humans are involved in old age. When researchers explore why this could happen, the answer is almost uniformly artisans are not as attractive wages to work in other types of jobs.

4. Environmental Impact

All the textile industry there is an element of the coloring process inevitably produced wastewater. Liquid waste from tie-dyed cloth is not environmentally friendly. Entrepreneurs in tie-dyed cloth should plan early on the waste that will be produced if want to plunge as tie-dyed cloth manufacturers. In fact there is a craftsman who sacrificed their household water consumption is not from the well water, but chose to use water from the local water company (PDAM). In order to fulfill the purposes of tie-dyed cloth production using well water in his backyard.

5. Uniqueness Motives

The end results or the expression of creativity in the design pattern / motif is an attraction that makes consumers will decide the purchase. As a product of creative economics, then the tie-dyed fabric should be managed by an entrepreneur with good quality management capabilities, and final consumer oriented (Kachba, et al, 2012). This is very different with the process of cloth batik which is always clearable during the production process. Tie-dyed cloth requires a strong imagination in casting the pattern, the steps are performed in the dyeing process until the final results are obtained.

Due to the tie-dyed cloth designer must have a strong imagination, then to create the successful product in the market, the designer of tie-dyed cloth should also be appropriate in determining the market segment that will be entered (Kachba, et al, 2012).

6. Uniformity of Motive

Quality being the commander in winning competitive products on the market. The quality has varied definitions, including the stability of the product specifications of each production. Results of the process of making tie-dyed cloth have heterogeneity in product specifications. This is possible because the end product / coloring of

the tie-dyed cloth production can be controlled at least compared to all existing cloth production in which the coloring stage.

This heterogeneity can be defined as a product that is not good, because the artisans can not produce the same cloth, at different times, even in the same person. However, behind this weakness, the reality of the results of the tie-dyed cloth can be defined as the excess cloth than the tie-dyed batik. Proverb that reads your weakness is your strength very precise in positioning adage used as tie-dyed cloth products forward.

7. Production Speed

In addition to the benefits of the product, the quality, timeliness of delivery and flexibility in customizing the products consumers desire, there is one more factor that consumers consider in the purchase of the products. It is the production speed (Anli, et al, 2007). Production speed can be the answer to consumer demand. Thus, the speed of production becomes an element that is very considered in developing a creative industrial area, because it directly affects the size of the labor absorption. The speed of tie-dyed cloth production is strongly influenced how many points to be tied (counteraction color when dyeing) and how many times the number of immersion to be done.

In addition, tie-dyed cloth production speed is also greatly influenced by long-presence and strong least the sun rays are used when drying after dyeing. Because drying naturally (with the help of sunlight), the tie-dyed cloth production speed can not be forced. Such things because all artisans tie-dyed cloth are included in the category of small industries, some even including household industries. Even most of the workers are women (Pinta, 2013), so it has the slow potential of production speed.

8. Distribution Outlets

Ease of customers to obtain the product sought is not only influenced by the purchasing power of consumers, but also influenced by the distribution mechanism of the top manufacturers of produced products (OECD, (2000); Limakrisna, Sudarso and Daryus, 2015). What meaning can produce quality goods if products are hard to find on the market, so consumers can be moved to buy the products of its competitors.

In fact mentions that the consumer markets tie-dyed cloth spread out geographically, meaning that consumers tie-dyed cloth is not only concentrated in one particular area. To that end, the ability of artisans to bring the product (tie-dyed cloth) to the consumer to be one of the factors that determine consumer chooses tie-dyed cloth is sought.

The existence of outlets, stores, show room of tie-dyed cloth into the factors that determine the success rate of tie-dyed cloth in penetrating the market. In terms of distribution (outlets, stores, show room) of tie-dyed cloth in general still less than batik cloth. To that end, this fact should be concerned to artisans of tie-dyed cloth. Request for tie-dyed cloth so great in the first 6 months in 2015 (due to the effect of marriage Raffi Ahmad and also Gibran Raka Bumi) can not be maximized by craftsmen. In addition to the production process that is not short, the existence of stores, outlets or show room becomes a limiting factor. While it can not be denied that the inability to meet this market demand due to factors over which far exceeds the ability of artisans to produce tie-dyed cloth being produced.

9. Technology Mastery

Apart from the speed factor producing the tie-dyed cloth, pushed technology and pulled to demand (Theinsathid, Chandrachai and Keeratipibul, (2009); Di Stefano, Gambardella and Verona, 2012) are important factors in determining the quality of products produced in small and micro enterprises (Soriano, et al, 2002). Basically tie-dyed cloth manufacturing technology has been mastered, because of tie-dyed technology is the result of work and intention sons of the Indonesian nation, especially from Yogyakarta City.

Competitive Strategy Formulation of Tie-Dyed Cloth

As a creative product, tie-dyed cloth must rely on the creativity of the craftsmen (Marques and Ferreira, 2009). When examined over the course of the development of tie-dyed cloth, it seems less so creativity or innovation of artisans. Stagnation of creativity is not separated from the artisans age. They are craftsmen who have "played" since tens of years ago, so that is produced today is nothing more than a continuation of the creativity that are generated when a young man.

Creative economy relies on the dynamics of creativity and innovation (Marques and Ferreira, 2009) requires actors to have a change of character. Changes in the human character are only owned by the younger generation, for the government should facilitate to encourage a young people spirit to want to plunge the tie-dyed cloth creative industries in Yogyakarta City. Karakter inovatif generasi muda akan mempengaruhi perilaku kinerja perusahaan dimana generasi muda tersebut bekerja (Acquaah, 2007). Menurut Pisanu dan Minapace (2014), sebuah inovasi harus mengandung lima

karakter, yaitu motivasi, bakat, minat, keterampilan dan pengetahuan; yang kesemuanya biasanya ada pada diri generasi muda.

In addition, tie-dyed cloth should be developed with clear goals through the right innovation of creating process (Marques and Ferreira, 2009). Considering the batik cloth is the main competitor product of tie-dyed cloth, the formulation of development strategies tie-dyed cloth should always be compared with those attributes into consideration the consumer (Coyle, Bardi and Langley, 2003) in making tie-dyed cloth purchasing against product competitors (batik), then it could be known the sell of quality products (Johnston, R, 1995). The quality performance of comparison attributes tie-dyed cloth and batik cloth in this study can be seen in Table 1 below:

Table 1. Comparison of Attribute Values Than the Tie-Dyed Fabric Batik Cloth						
No	Key Success Factors (atribut)	Weight	Tie-Dyed Cloth		Batik Cloth	
			Rank	Score	Rank	Score
1	Pricing Product	0.1500	3	0.45	2	0.30
2	Product Quality	0.1700	3	0.51	4	0.68
3	Absorption of Labor	0.1400	3	0.42	3	0.42
4	Environmental Impact	0.1500	3	0.45	3	0.45
5	Uniqueness Motives	0.0700	3	0.21	2	0.14
6	Uniformity of Motive	0.0600	2	0.12	3	0.18
7	Production Speed	0.0400	2	0.08	2	0.08
8	Distribution Outlets	0.1600	2	0.32	4	0.64
9	Technology Mastery	0.0600	3	0.18	4	0.24
	Total	1.0000		2.74		3.13

Source: Primary Data Analysis

Based on Table 1 above, the important success factors that tie-dyed cloth rank value higher than batik cloth only two, namely the pricing products and the uniqueness of motives. Based on these two advantages, the recommendations given to developing industrial centers of tie-dyed cloth are positioning status of a product that has its uniqueness in each product. With a title as a unique product (which is not easily imitated) and includes new products among fans of batik, tie-dyed cloth then makes consistent increasingly as creative products. The success of tie-dyed cloth on the market should be supported by a good service to customers. Compilation of good positioning products and services will be producing in sustainable profits (Didonet and Diaz, 2012).

A product that has a unique character, have consequences bother-easy to enter the broad market. However, the unique product can still be used as a mass product (having a large market share) apabila terdapat perbaikan didalam proses produksinya (Kaminski, Olivera and Lopes, 2008). It means, in this context, tie-dyed cloth can be used as a mass product if the product substance was same perception as the good quality products. Tie-dyed cloth has potential as a product that is fully sustainable innovation if supported local governments through a uniform policy for civil servants and school children as recommended Saheed (2013) the similar research in Nigeria.

This paradigm has proved to tie-dyed cloth in the last one year. Demand for tie-dyed cloth jumps away than before. The increasing demand occurred after Raffi Ahmad marriage with Nagita Slavina. During the ceremony spray (16-10-2014), brides are both using tie-dyed cloth.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

1. Factors to be considered a buyer in the purchasing of tie-dyed cloth in the city of Yogyakarta and Solo is the price of products, product quality, absorption of labor, environmental impact, unique motifs, uniformity of motive, speed of production, distribution outlets and technology mastery.
2. Competitive strategy of tie-dyed cloth faces batik cloth in the domestic and international markets is a tie-dyed cloth should be positioned as a product that is unique (unlimited edition), then the tie-dyed cloth could be pushed into such exclusive products, as displayed as some tie-dyed cloth artisans in Yogyakarta City.

Suggestion

1. The Government and craftsmen of tie-dyed cloth should be consistent in mapping the position of the rivalry between the and tie-dyed and batik cloth.
2. By considering the advantages and disadvantages of tie-dyed cloth to batik cloth, the tie-dyed cloth could be pushed into such exclusive products displayed some tie-dyed cloth artisans in the City of Yogyakarta.

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